

Marketing Strategy for Black Tea Products Using SOAR Analysis at PT. Rolas Nusantara Mandiri Surabaya

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ABSTRACT: Indonesia is recognized for its vast and fertile agricultural landscapes, encompassing a wide variety of crops, tea being one of them. The potential of cultivating tea in Indonesia is demonstrated by the presence of extensive state-owned plantations (SOP) and the multitude of tea beverage brands in the market. However, the high SOP production does not guarantee that the tea products produced by state-owned enterprises (SOE's) will be recognized and have a strong brand in the minds of the Indonesian people. One such brand is Rolas Tea, managed by PT. Rolas Nusantara Mandiri, which has not been able to break into the top six brands in the Top Brand category for loose-leaf or bagged tea. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the appropriate marketing strategies to break into the top six brands. The research objectives are to analyze internal-external factors, formulate alternative marketing strategies for black tea products, and determine the priority and recommendation of marketing strategies. The research uses a qualitative and quantitative approach and is conducted in Surabaya. Four informants were purposively selected, and data were collected through primary and secondary sources. The analysis methods used include descriptive analysis, IFE and EFE matrices, the IE matrix for PT. RNM, SOAR analysis resulting in six alternative strategies, and the QSPM matrix. The research findings indicate that the IFE matrix score is 3.19 and the EFE matrix score is 3.58. The IE matrix places PT. RNM in quadrant I, the SOAR analysis yields six alternative strategies, and the QSPM matrix identifies strategy 3 as the top priority, which is market penetration with a TAS score of 8.00.

KEYWORDS: Marketing Strategy, Black Tea, IFE and EFE, IE, SOAR, and QSPM

I. INTRODUCTION

Tea is a popular agricultural product extensively grown in Indonesia. This trend can be attributed to the increasing consumption of tea among the Indonesian population. As noted by T. Anggraini (2017), the practice of tea consumption has gradually become deeply rooted in Indonesian society, as evidenced by the widespread habit of keeping tea in Indonesian households. This situation is reinforced by the presence of suitable land for cultivating tea in Indonesia, as emphasized by the Center for Plantation Research and Development (2010). They pointed out that tea, being a subtropical crop, thrives particularly well in the hilly regions of Indonesia. According to data from the Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS, 2022), the tea production in Indonesia during the previous five years has been chiefly defined by the presence of State Plantations, contributing to 39.19% of the overall output. Smallholder Plantations follow closely at 35.62%, and Private Large Plantations come in third at 25.19%. With State Plantations playing such a significant and leading role in tea production, it is reasonable to expect that state-owned enterprises would be responsible for creating high-quality tea products that earn recognition and popularity among the Indonesian population. On the contrary, the 2023 data from TopBrand presents a contrasting picture. In the loose-leaf or bagged tea products category, the top six positions are occupied by tea brands from private companies, with no presence from state-owned enterprises like Rolas Tea. This contradicts the BPS data, which highlights the significant dominance of State Plantations in tea production over the past five years.

Rolas Tea is a tea brand that is under the ownership of the state-owned company PT. Rolas Nusantara Mandiri (PT. RNM). PT. RNM, as a subsidiary of PTPN XII, is involved in the production of various plantation crops, including coffee and tea. PT. RNM is well-equipped to produce high-quality tea products because it manages four tea gardens, ensuring a secure and quality supply of raw materials. One of PT. RNM's notable strengths lies in its black tea product. Over the last five years, black tea products have dominated the volume of tea sales, accounting for 94.49%, while green tea and white tea make up the

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remaining 5.51%. The potential for developing black tea isn't just due to its high sales volume but also because it's easier to produce on a large scale. Another reason for the greater potential of black tea is the broader and more diverse market it enjoys compared to green tea and white tea, which tend to have more limited markets.

PT. RNM primarily depends on traditional marketing methods, including their depots, owned outlets, and collaborations with various retail partners. They are in the early stages of developing digital marketing strategies, utilizing platforms like Shopee, Lazada, Tokopedia, Bukalapak, as well as websites and social media channels such as TikTok and Instagram @Officialrollas. However, their digital marketing efforts have not been fully optimized. This is evident in the lack of well-planned and focused posts, the absence of organized posting schedules, and incomplete product information on their websites and online marketplaces. Exactly, this situation stands in opposition to the advice provided by Haidar & Martadi (2021), highlighting the importance of prioritizing the management of visual content to foster customer loyalty and engagement.

Based on the challenges faced by the Rolas Tea brand, including its inability to secure a spot in the top six of the Top Brand Index, the struggle with visibility compared to other tea brands, a reliance on traditional marketing methods, and under-optimized digital marketing efforts, PT. RNM requires the most appropriate marketing strategy to enhance the Rolas Tea brand. Consequently, it is essential to conduct research under the title "Marketing Strategy for Black Tea Products Using SOAR Analysis at PT. Rolas Nusantara Mandiri Surabaya" with three primary objectives: first, to identify and analyze internal and external factors influencing the marketing strategy for black tea products at PT. RNM; second, to devise alternative marketing strategies for black tea products at PT. RNM; and finally, to establish priorities and offer recommendations for marketing strategies for black tea products at PT. RNM.

II. LITERATUR RIVIEW

A. *Black Tea*

T. Anggraini (2017) In 1648 *Camellia sinensis* was the first type of tea to enter Indonesia in the form of seeds. L. D. Anggraini *et al.* (2018) The tea plant can be divided into four types based on the processing process, namely oolong tea, black tea, green tea, and white tea. Black tea is the most dominant type of tea consumed by people in the world as much as 69% of the 3.4 million tons of total world tea consumption in 2007 (BPTP Jabar, 2013). Pusat Penelitian dan Pengembangan Perkebunan (2010) The growing conditions of tea plants can be seen from the climate, namely air temperature between 13-15 ° C, during the day relative humidity > 70%, requiring protective trees if the location of the plantation is getting higher, and soil fertility with acidity 4.5-5.6 (andisol soil).

Tea can be processed by both the CTC and Orthodox methods, but in both methods black tea is a type of tea that goes through a process of enzymatic oxidation stages (T. Anggraini, 2017). According to Rohdiana (2015) Black tea production using the CTC method tends to be shorter than the orthodox method, because the CTC method's withering process is 5 hours faster, besides that in the CTC method there is a drying stage which aims to stop the enzymatic oxidation process. Black tea tends to be consumed more by the public because it has a comfortable taste on the tongue, and has many good contents such as catechins, essential oils, caffeine, vitamins A, B, C and polyphenols.

B. *Marketing strategy*

Riyanto (2022) Strategic management is the activity of managing various strategic decisions of a company with three hierarchical levels, namely generic strategy, main strategy, and functional strategy. David (2011) There are four generic strategies, namely vertical integration, intensive strategy, diversification strategy, and defensive strategy. David (2011) Adding that the main strategy is a more specific strategy than the generic strategy mode. Rahim & Radjab (2017) Functional strategies are strategies that are very technical in nature, have a shorter timeframe and the executors are each division in the company such as the marketing, operations, finance, human resources, and research and development divisions.

Assauri (2020) Marketing strategy is a strategy that manages various policies and rules to achieve the company's marketing goals and objectives at each level as a step to face intense competition. Humairaa (2021) stated that marketing strategy is an activity to create and innovate to achieve company goals with fresh methods so that customers are loyal to the company. Marketing strategy will be easier to carry out if it fulfills the elements of marketing strategy as stated by Rangkuti (1998) which states that the elements of marketing strategy are elements of competitive strategy where this strategy is a strategy for seizing market power which is more specifically divided into three, namely based on segmentation, targeting, and positioning. The next element is the marketing tactics element which aims to introduce products with strategies that are different from competitors, and finally is the marketing value element where product quality becomes the main value to gain customer loyalty.

C. *Matriks IFE, EFE dan IE*

Riyanto (2022) The IFE (Internal Factor Evaluation) matrix is a matrix used to analyze the internal environment of the company. Hidayatullah *et al.* (2020) The IFE matrix is a matrix that is carried out with the aim of knowing the level of strength and weakness of the internal conditions of a company. Sulasih (2019) The stages of analyzing the IFE matrix are simply as follows:

1. Identify internal key factors for Strengths and Aspirations
2. Giving weight to each internal key factor
3. Rating each internal key factor
4. Calculating the score of each internal key factor

Riyanto (2022) The EFE (External Factor Evaluation) matrix is a matrix that is carried out to find out various information in the company's external environment. In addition, according to Sari (2019) the EFE matrix can help companies to identify and evaluate external factors that have an impact and influence on the company. Riyanto (2022) The following are the steps to create an EFE matrix:

1. Identify external key factors for Opportunity and Result
2. Giving weight to each External key factor
3. Rating each external key factor
4. Calculating the score of each External key factor

The IE (Internal-External) matrix is a matrix commonly used by companies to formulate a strategy based on the company's position in the IE matrix (Qanita, 2020). More details are explained by Syamruddin (2020) which states that the IE matrix is a matrix used to determine the position and condition of the company through nine cells based on the results of the IFE matrix score (as the x axis) and EFE (as the y axis). Arrohmah & Rum (2022) Stating that the IE matrix consists of three strategies that are divided into each quadrant of the IE matrix as Sarfin *et al.* (2021) which states that the grow and build strategy for quadrant positions I, II, and IV, the hold and maintain strategy for quadrant positions III, V, and VII, and the harvest and divestiture strategy for quadrant positions VI, VIII, and IX.

D. *SOAR Analysis (Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results)*

Stavros & Cole (2013) SOAR analysis is an analysis used to identify the company's strengths to be applied to the opportunities the company has with a positive approach from strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and results. According to Hartuti & Rochdiani (2021) SOAR analysis has 5 stages to go through, namely the stages of Initiate, Inquiry, Imagine, Innovate, and Inspire to Implement. This is supported by the statement of Stavros & Cole (2013) which states that SOAR uses the 5I approach with the aim of showing the positive side of the company to stakeholders.

Hartuti & Rochdiani (2021) 5I, namely Initiate or the discussion stage regarding the direction of business development owned, second is the Inquiry stage or the investigation stage carried out to study and analyze the strength factors and opportunities owned by the company so that they can be utilized more optimally. The third is the Imagine stage, which is the stage carried out by providing views and expectations in the future regarding the direction of the business and what kind of company will be developed based on aspiration factors and desired results. The fourth stage is Innovate, which is the stage where the company begins to design various appropriate strategies from systems, programs, and integrated structures using the SOAR matrix. The last stage is Inspire to Implement, where at this stage the company can determine strategic decisions that are suitable for implementation.

E. *QSPM Matrix*

Riyanto (2022) The QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) matrix is an analytical method used by companies to compare and determine various alternative decisions to quantify the strategic decision-making process and minimize subjectivity. Maulidah (2012) Stated that the QSPM matrix is an analysis used to select the best strategic alternative using input from the three stages that have been passed. The first stage in question is the IFE and EFE matrix, the second stage is the IE matrix and SOAR analysis, and the third stage is analysis through this QSPM matrix.

Based on the literature review, the existence of a large black tea consumption potential in the world, the importance of the right marketing strategy to achieve company goals, the IFE EFE matrix function to determine the internal and external conditions of the company, the IE matrix function and SOAR matrix analysis to design alternative strategies, and the QSPM matrix function to determine strategy priorities make this research appropriate to answer the research objectives.

III. RESEARCH AND METODOLOGI

The research is being conducted at PT. Rolas Nusantara Mandiri, which is situated in the city of Surabaya. The choice of this location is deliberate and based on specific factors. This decision to select this research site is primarily because PT. RNM is a subsidiary of a state-owned enterprise (SOE's) with great potential, focusing on the production and marketing of premium black tea products, a product that isn't widely recognized in the market. Furthermore, PT. RNM heavily relies on traditional marketing methods, manages digital marketing less effectively, and grapples with challenges related to the brand's visibility when compared to other tea brands. The selection of participants or informants follows the purposive approach, involving the choice of four key informants based on distinct considerations and criteria. These four informants comprise the head of the marketing division, the production coordinator, QC and licensing personnel, the head of the accounting and HR division, and the marketing and sales coordinator. Data collection methods encompass a combination of primary and secondary data sources. The method of descriptive data analysis is utilized to illustrate and characterize the research data. In this particular study, it serves the purpose of outlining the company's profile and interpreting the research findings. These findings encompass the description of the analysis of internal and external factors, alternative marketing strategies, the highest-priority marketing strategy, and recommendations for marketing approaches that can be put into practice by PT. RNM.

The IFE matrix analysis is executed by enumerating various internal company factors through a focus group discussion (FGD) system. The critical internal factors are then grouped into strengths and aspirations to facilitate assessment. On the other hand, the EFE matrix analysis involves listing the company's external factors, using both FGD and similar research sources. Key external factors are subsequently classified into opportunities and desired outcomes for evaluation.

- Weight Formula = Sum of the ratings of the four informants on each attribute / Total Sum
- Rating Formula = Sum of informant ratings on each attribute / number of informants
- Scor Formula = Weight x Rating

The steps to analyze the IFE-EFE matrix are as follows:

1. Identification of internal-external key factors through FGDs and from similar research sources
2. Weighting each key factor by giving each informant a weight of 1-4 with the criteria 1 = very bad, 2 = medium, 3 = above average, and 4 = superior. The weight of each key factor is obtained through the weight formula
3. Rating is done according to the rating formula
4. Calculate the score according to the scor formula. The total score in the IFE matrix will be the total IFE score and the total score in the EFE matrix will be the total EFE score.

IE matrix analysis is carried out with reference to the total IFE value and the total EFE value. The total IFE value is on the X axis and the total EFE value is on the Y axis. Each axis is divided into 3 categories which parameterize the current position of the PT RNM company and the appropriate strategy to be used in that position. The intersection of the total IFE and EFE values will be the point where the quadrant position of the PT RNM company is located. The following is an image of the IE matrix:

Picture 1. Internal-Eksternal Matrix

Source: David (2011)

SOAR analysis is a methodology centered on identifying strengths to leverage existing opportunities by way of aspirations, with the ultimate goal of achieving desired results. It leads to the formulation of alternative strategies, encompassing strengths-aspirations (SA strategies), strengths-results (SR strategies), opportunities-aspirations (OA strategies), and opportunities-results

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(OR strategies). These strategies, originating from this amalgamation, are firmly grounded in the insights provided by the IE matrix, ensuring that they remain in harmony with PT. RNM's existing situation and status.

SA strategies harness PT. RNM's strengths to materialize and bring to fruition their coveted aspirations. OA strategies spring to life through the exploitation of opportunities acquired by PT. RNM, enabling them to actively pursue and accomplish their aspirations. SR strategies are built on the foundation of the company's strengths to achieve the desired outcomes. Conversely, OR strategies involve adapting and capitalizing on the available opportunities to attain the sought-after results. These resultant strategies are always customized to the company's unique circumstances and position, as evaluated within the IE matrix.

QSPM matrix analysis is an analysis conducted to determine the marketing strategy priorities of Rolas Tea Black Tea products. QSPM matrix analysis can be done after going through the stages of IFE-EFE matrix analysis, IE matrix analysis, and SOAR matrix analysis. The QSPM matrix is as follows:

The steps for conducting a QSPM matrix analysis are as follows:

1. Internal and external key factors obtained through the IFE and EFE matrices
2. The weight column is obtained through the weight column in the IFE and EFE matrices
3. Create a column for each strategy obtained according to the number of alternative strategies obtained through the SOAR matrix starting from strategy1 to all alternative strategies
4. Calculate the AS (Attractiveness Scor) value of each key factor against each strategy by giving a score of 1-4 (1 = not attractive, 2 = somewhat attractive, 3 = quite attractive, 4 = very attractive)
5. Calculating TAS (Total Attractiveness Scores) with the formula $\text{Weight} \times \text{AS}$ on each key factor
6. Calculating the sum of the TAS of each strategy

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Internal-External Factor Analysis

Analysis of internal and external factors is carried out using IFE and EFE matrix analysis. This analysis was conducted to answer the first objective of the study. The four informants provided an assessment of each key internal and external factor by answering questions from the interview guide sheet. The following are the results of the IFE and EFE matrix analysis:

Table 5. Results of IFE Matrix Analysis

No.	Key Factors / Internal Attributes	Sum	Weight	Rating	Scor
<i>Strengths</i>					
1.	Superior black tea products	14	0.13	3.50	0.45
2.	Diligent and unwavering compliance with Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs).	16	0.15	4.00	0.58
3.	Implement promotional activities that provide educational value to consumers.	12	0.11	3.00	0.33
4.	Possessing a multitude of tea plantations, leading to a wide range of unique black tea profiles.	14	0.13	3.50	0.45
5.	The supply of raw materials is more secure due to having its own plantations, ensuring sustainability.	14	0.13	3.50	0.45
6.	Marketing the product through a partnership with the agrotourism destination, Wonosari Tea Plantation, owned by PTPN XII.	13	0.12	3.25	0.38
Total		83	0.75	20.75	2.63
<i>Aspirations</i>					
1.	Forming collaborations with influencers to implement extensive marketing campaigns.	9	0.08	2.25	0.18
2.	Enhancing distributor partnerships through the provision of distinctive advantages and specified profit margins.	10	0.09	2.50	0.23
3.	Organizational restructuring involving the establishment of an R&D department to support business development at PT. RNM.	8	0.07	2.00	0.15
Total		27	0.25	6.75	0.56
Overall Total		110	1.00	27.50	3.19

Source: Primary data after processing (2023)

Based on the results of the IFE matrix analysis above, the total score of the IFE matrix is 3.19, with the key internal factor that is the primary strength of PT. RNM being "strict and consistent implementation of SOPs" with a score of 0.58. This indicates that all

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of PT. RNM's staff have implemented the existing SOPs, which has led to a more structured and coordinated work environment. The implementation of SOPs helps minimize the risk of errors in both the production and post-production processes. Additionally, it contributes to improving staff performance, thus aiding in achieving the company's objectives. This aligns with the findings of Nabilla & Hasin (2022), who stated that the purpose and function of SOPs are to guide employees in carrying out their tasks for more effective and efficient work. This statement is also supported by the research of Marlina et al. (2021), which states that the implementation of SOPs in companies has a significant impact on employee discipline.

The primary internal factor that serves as the top aspiration for PT. RNM is "Enhancing distributor partnerships through the provision of distinctive advantages and specified profit margins" with a score of 0.23. This aspirational factor is crucial and should be promptly pursued while carefully selecting suitable partners to ensure the company's objectives are achieved. Partner compatibility is ensured through exploratory stages to ascertain shared visions, missions, and a mutual desire to introduce Rolas Tea black tea products to a broader market and break into the top brand index, thus increasing sales volume. This aligns with the findings of Kurniawan et al. (2023), which state that a partnership strategy involving distributor and reseller partners is highly effective in introducing products to a wider consumer base, ultimately boosting sales.

Table 6. Results of EFE Matrix Analysis

No.	Key Factors/Eksternal Attributes	Sum	Weight	Rating	Scor
<i>Opportunity</i>					
1.	The products produced do not conflict with the culture of the community.	15	0.15	3.75	0.56
2.	The increasing awareness of the public regarding tea as a beverage product with numerous health benefits due to its antioxidant content.	15	0.15	3.75	0.56
3.	The evolution and changing mindset of society that is beginning to adopt a culture of healthy living.	14	0.14	3.50	0.49
4.	The market development potential is still significant and ongoing because black tea is a commonly consumed tea variety in Indonesian society.	14	0.14	3.50	0.49
Total		58	0.58	14.5	2.11
<i>Results</i>					
1.	The product becomes more widely known and can penetrate various segments	14	0.14	3.50	0.49
2.	Gain more business partners and increase sales volume	15	0.15	3.75	0.56
3.	The company becomes more innovative and sensitive to opportunities	13	0.13	3.25	0.42
Total		42	0.42	10.50	1.48
Overall Total		100	1.00	25.00	3.58

Source: Primary data after processing (2023)

The EFE matrix analysis results show that the total EFE matrix score is 3.58, with the key external factor representing the primary opportunity being the factor that "the products produced do not contradict the culture of the community." In other words, Rolas Tea black tea products are embraced by the existing culture in Indonesia without violating local customs, traditions, or norms, and this is indicated by a score of 0.56. This presents an opportunity that PT. RNM should harness to expand the marketing of Rolas Tea black tea, making it more widely known among the population and potentially even establishing itself as a daily consumption habit. This opportunity is reinforced by the external factor, "the increasing public awareness of tea as a beverage with numerous health benefits due to its antioxidant content," which is also a significant opportunity with an equal score of 0.56. This aligns with the findings of Suhairi et al. (2023), which suggest that the perceptions of local Indonesians toward foreign cultures hold substantial value from an international marketing perspective and can significantly impact the level of product acceptance within the local community.

The key external factor that is highly anticipated as an outcome is the factor of "gaining many business partners and increasing sales volume," with a score of 0.56. This means that PT. RNM should make the most of the strengths and opportunities available to realize this topmost aspiration, which involves acquiring numerous business partners and boosting the sales volume of Rolas Tea black tea. This aligns with the research conducted by Chandra et al. (2014), which suggests that in order to enhance business collaboration and increase sales volume at Media Print stores, it is essential to expand the number of business partner

B. Marketing Strategy Alternatives

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Alternative marketing strategies are analyzed using the IE matrix and SOAR matrix. The IE matrix analysis is used to determine the current position and condition of PT RNM, while the SOAR matrix is used to formulate alternative marketing strategies for rolas tea black tea products at PT RNM.

Picture 2. Results of the IE Matrix Analysis of PT. RNM

Source: Primary data after processing (2023)

The total score of the IFE matrix, which is 3.19, indicates that PT. RNM's internal factors are categorized as "Strong," while the total score of the EFE matrix, which is 3.58, suggests that PT. RNM's external factors fall under the category of "High." Based on the total score of the IFE matrix being 3.19 and the EFE matrix being 3.58, it indicates a coordinate point that positions PT. RNM in Quadrant I. Quadrant I signifies that PT. RNM's current condition is in the "Grow & Build" phase, where the appropriate strategy to implement involves intensive strategies such as market development, product development, and market penetration. This is supported by Gunawan's (2017) statement that intensive strategies are suitable for companies in a growth phase, involving market penetration and market development.

Once the position and condition of PT. RNM are understood, the design of alternative marketing strategies can be undertaken using a SOAR analysis, based on the results of the IE matrix analysis, which suggests the types of strategies suitable for PT. RNM's current situation. This aligns with Hartuti & Rochdiani's (2021) statement that the fourth stage of SOAR analysis is innovation, where a company can design various strategies, programs, and systems to become more integrated using the SOAR matrix. The results of the SOAR matrix analysis are as follows:

Table 7. Results of SOAR Matrix Analysis

	Strengths	Opportunities
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Superior black tea products Diligent and unwavering compliance with Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs). Implement promotional activities that provide educational value to consumers. Possessing a multitude of tea plantations, leading to a wide range of unique black tea profiles. The supply of raw materials is more secure due to having its own plantations, ensuring sustainability. Marketing the product through a partnership with the agrotourism destination, Wonosari Tea Plantation, owned by PTPN XII. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The products produced do not conflict with the culture of the community. The increasing awareness of the public regarding tea as a beverage product with numerous health benefits due to its antioxidant content. The evolution and changing mindset of society that is beginning to adopt a culture of healthy living. The market development potential is still significant and ongoing because black tea is a commonly consumed tea variety in Indonesian society.
Aspirations	SA	OA

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<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Forming collaborations with influencers to implement extensive marketing campaigns. Enhancing distributor partnerships through the provision of distinctive advantages and specified profit margins. Organizational restructuring involving the establishment of an R&D department to support business development at PT. RNM. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Focus on a deeper understanding of customer segments and identifying specific segments that allow for the selection of influencers aligned with product characteristics. This will enable more targeted and effective marketing, using the Market Development strategy (S1, S4, S5, A1). Implement stricter monitoring and assessment of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to ensure that the production and post-production sectors operate in a more harmonious and integrated manner. This will enhance efficiency and effectiveness in internal marketing and integration (Internal/Internal Integration) (S2, A3) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Create an engaging campaign that emphasizes the consumption of natural and healthy products to boost the confidence of loyal customers (existing market) in consuming the product. This aligns with Market Penetration (O1, O2, O3, A1). Develop ready-to-drink black tea products in bottle packaging (Product Development), which corresponds to opportunities (O4) and specific actions (A2, A3).
Results	SR	OR
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The product becomes more widely known and can penetrate various segments Gain more business partners and increase sales volume The company becomes more innovative and sensitive to opportunities 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Increase educational promotions by arranging tours for tea garden visitors to the tea bag and loose tea production facilities (market penetration). This strategy leverages the company's strengths (S1, S3, S4, S6) and addresses pertinent issues and concerns (R1). 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborate with health organizations and relevant institutions focusing on health and well-being to support the promotion of the product, thereby increasing its credibility (market development). This aligns with opportunities (O1, O2).

Source: Primary data after processing (2023)

Here is an explanation for each of the alternative strategies:

- Strategy 1: This represents a market development approach centered on refining customer segments and targeting specific groups to identify appropriate influencers for the promotion of Rolas Tea's black tea products. The objective is to execute precise and efficient marketing by capitalizing on the product's strengths, which include its high quality, distinctive flavor, and the use of top-quality raw materials sourced from the company's tea gardens.
- Strategy 2: This strategy places emphasis on internal integration by imposing rigorous monitoring and evaluation of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The goal is to ensure seamless synchronization between the production and post-production sectors. The consistent implementation of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) is intended to enhance the quality of Rolas Tea products and enhance the performance of the staff. This strategy also acknowledges the escalating risks associated with a company's growth.
- Strategy 3: This approach is a market penetration strategy that involves crafting an appealing campaign underscoring the consumption of natural and healthful products. It underscores the quality and composition of Rolas Tea's black tea, which is free from preservatives and is made exclusively from 100% tea leaves.
- Strategy 4: This strategy revolves around product development and encompasses the creation of pre-packaged, ready-to-drink black tea products in bottle packaging. It leverages PT. RNM's expertise and capabilities in producing bottled water.
- Strategy 5: This strategy is a market penetration approach that prioritizes the intensification of educational marketing campaigns via guided tours of the tea bag and loose tea production facilities. This strategy is deemed essential, as recommended by Wibowo et al. (2018), for educational promotional efforts.
- Strategy 6: This represents another market development strategy that entails partnering with healthcare institutions and similar organizations to advocate for the health advantages of Rolas Tea's black tea products, with the aim of boosting their credibility and perceived benefits.

C. The prioritized marketing strategies and provide detailed recommendations based on the QSPM analysis

The selection of priority marketing strategies and recommendations for marketing strategies is carried out through an analysis using the Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM). Priority marketing strategies are the most crucial strategies to be

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implemented first, based on the current situation of PT. RNM, as reflected in the Total Attractiveness Score. Here are the outcomes of the QSPM analysis:

Table 8. Results of QSPM Matrix Analysis

Strategy Rating	TAS
1 Strategy 3 (Market Penetration): Launch an engaging campaign that underscores the consumption of natural and healthy products, thereby boosting the confidence of loyal customers in product consumption. Emphasize the product's quality and its natural, preservative-free composition, which comprises 100% tea leaves. This aligns with Market Penetration efforts, making it the primary marketing strategy.	8,00
2 Strategy 6 (Market Development): Foster collaborations with health agencies and organizations dedicated to health and well-being, aimed at advocating and promoting the products for increased credibility. This strategy is a significant aspect of Market Development, which warrants its inclusion as a priority.	7,87
3 Strategy 1 (Market Development): Enhance market development by refining customer segments and pinpointing specific segments to identify suitable influencers, enabling more precise and targeted marketing efforts. This strategy complements Strategy 6 in Market Development and should be executed concurrently.	7,78
4 Strategy 5 (Market Penetration): Intensify educational promotions by offering guided tours for visitors from tea gardens to the tea bag and brewed tea production facilities. This approach is pivotal in Market Penetration, thus meriting a place among the prioritized strategies.	7,78
5 Strategy 2 (Internal Integration): Enforce stricter supervision and assessment of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to ensure synchronization between the production and post-production sectors. Consistent adherence to Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) can enhance product quality and staff performance. This internal integration strategy is crucial for overall efficiency.	7,70
6 Strategy 4 (Product Development): Develop a ready-to-drink black tea product in bottle packaging. Leveraging PT. RNM's experience and capabilities in producing bottled water, this strategy addresses product development and caters to a different market segment.	6,22

Source: Primary data after processing (2023)

Based on the QSPM matrix analysis, the prioritized marketing strategy for Rolas Tea black tea products is as follows:

1. Strategy 3 - Market Penetration (Total Attractiveness Score: 8.00): This strategy involves creating an engaging campaign that emphasizes the consumption of natural and healthy products, aiming to boost customer confidence and loyalty in consuming Rolas Tea black tea products. Leveraging both conventional and digital marketing channels is supported by PT RNM's existing marketing media. This approach aligns with research indicating that social marketing campaigns for healthy foods must be tailored to the audience and be long-term, as behavioral changes require time for acceptance and application.
2. Strategy 6 (Total Attractiveness Score: 7.87): This strategy focuses on collaborating with health agencies and similar institutions to enhance trust in Rolas Tea black tea products. Health agencies can serve as expert endorsers, as studies suggest that consumers are influenced by the consumption behavior of credible endorsers. Recommendations from trustworthy endorsers can influence consumer product choices.
3. Strategy 1 (Total Attractiveness Score: 7.78): This is a market development strategy that involves segment clarification and targeting specific segments, allowing digital marketing with influencers to be carried out by selecting suitable talent. The choice of influencers is crucial and should align with the designated segment, as consumers' purchasing decisions through influencer promotions are influenced by content quality and interactions.
4. Strategy 5 (Total Attractiveness Score: 7.78): This market penetration strategy includes educational promotions through factory tours and product purchases, which leave a positive impression on consumers. Research suggests that tourism-based promotions and product innovation significantly impact increasing sales volume.
5. Strategy 2 (Total Attractiveness Score: 7.70): This strategy emphasizes strict KPI supervision and assessment to synchronize production and post-production sectors, ensuring improved service and product quality. This approach is in line with the importance of monitoring employee performance and adherence to established rules and regulations.
6. Strategy 4 (Total Attractiveness Score: 6.22): This product development strategy involves diversifying products by packaging Rolas Tea black tea in bottles. Leveraging PT. RNM's experience in producing bottled drinking water, this strategy acknowledges the influence of packaging quality on purchasing decisions.
7. Therefore, the top priority marketing strategy for Rolas Tea black tea products, with a Total Attractiveness Score of 8.00, is ****Strategy 3 - Market Penetration**** through compelling campaigns promoting natural and healthy products. To

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establish Rolas Tea as a top brand, it is recommended to consistently and continuously combine Strategy 3 with Strategy 1. This approach should yield a positive impact on brand recognition and consumer loyalty.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research, several key conclusions can be drawn:

- a. The internal and external factor analysis indicates that PT RNM has a strong internal position (IFE score of 3.19) and faces favorable external conditions (EFE score of 3.58). This suggests that the company is in a robust position to implement marketing strategies.
- b. The IE matrix positions PT RNM in quadrant I, characterized by "Grow & Build" conditions. This indicates that the company is well-positioned for growth and development.
- c. The SOAR matrix analysis yields 6 alternative marketing strategies, providing a range of options for PT RNM to consider.
- d. The QSPM analysis prioritizes Strategy 3, "Market Penetration," with a Total Attractiveness Score (TAS) of 8.00, making it the top priority marketing strategy.
- e. The recommended approach for Rolas Tea black tea products is to consistently and continuously combine Strategy 3 with Strategy 1. This strategy combination aims to penetrate the top brand index and further enhance the brand's recognition and customer loyalty.

These findings provide a comprehensive framework for PT RNM to follow in developing and implementing marketing strategies for Rolas Tea black tea products.

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